

11. N.Jumaxo‘ja. Satrlar silsilasidagi sehr. Toshkent: 1996. –Б. 23.
12. Мадаев.О. Ўзбек халқ оғзаки ижоди. – Т.: Мумтоз сўз. 2011. 200 б
13. Навоий, Алишер. Қаро кўзум. Т.: Адабиёт ва санъат нашриёти, 1987. — 768 б.
14. Оқ олма, қизил олма. Қўшиқлар. – Т.: 1972. -Б 28.

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND PROVERBS, THEIR FUNCTIONS IN SPEECH

Panayeva Qunduzxon Salay qizi

National University of Uzbekistan

Foreign philology faculty, foreign language and literature department

Master’s degree student,

Scientific adviser: Associate prof, PhD Abdullaeva N.E.

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Annotation: This thesis gives information about one of the main current issues of linguistics, proverbs and phrasal units, and their function in speech. The origin of proverbs, their characteristics were also studied. Proverbs were analyzed to reveal different situations in English.

Key words: Proverbs, paremies, phraseological units, saying, paremiography, aphorism, motto, epigram.

The vocabulary system of any language is enriched not only by words but also by phraseological units. Phraseological units are word-groups that cannot be created during the process of speech, they exist in the language as ready-made word groups

They are compiled in special dictionaries. The same as words phraseological units express a single notion and are used in a sentence as one part of it. American and British lexicographers call such units as idioms. We can mention such dictionaries as: L.Smith, Words and Idioms, V.Collins, ABook of English Idioms.

In these dictionaries we can find words, peculiar in their semantics (idiomatic), side by side with word-groups and sentences. In these dictionaries they are arranged, as a rule, into different semantic groups.

Phraseological units can be classified according to the ways they are formed, according to the degree of the motivation of their meaning, according to their structure and according to their part-of-speech meaning. A.V. Koonin classified phraseological units according to the way they are formed. He pointed out primary and secondary ways of forming phraseological units. By the classification of Academician V.Vinogradov phraseological units are divided into three groups: phraseological combinations, phraseological unities and phraseological fusions⁵³.

Proverb is a brief saying that presents a truth or some bit of useful wisdom. It is usually based on common sense or practical experience. The effect of a proverb is, to make the wisdom it tells seem to be self-evident⁵⁴. The same proverb often occurs among several different peoples. True proverbs are sayings that have been passed from generation to generation primarily by word of the mouth. They may also have been put into written form.

A proverb consists of a short sentence which contains a general piece of wisdom. A proverb contains wisdom which has been handed down from one generation to the next.

A proverb describes situations which happened before and which are repeated again and again.

Universal proverbs – On comparing proverbs of culturally unrelated parts of the world, one finds several one having not only the same basic idea but the form of expression, the wording is also identical or very similar. These are mainly simple expressions of simple observations or simple ethical concepts, but not all expressions of simple observations became proverbs in every language.

Regional proverbs – In culturally related regions, on the pattern of loan-words many loan-proverbs appear beside the indigenous ones. A considerable part of

⁵³ <https://mylektsii.su/8-67153.html>

⁵⁴ International Encyclopedia of Unified Science. – Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press. 1955

them can be traced back to the classical literature of the region's past, in Europe the Greco-Roman classics, and in the Far East to the Sanskrit and Korean classics.

Local Proverbs – In a cultural region often internal differences appear, the classics (the Bible or the Confucian Analects) are not equally regarded as a source of proverbs in every language. Geographical vicinity gives also rise to another set of common local proverbs. These considerations are illustrated in several European and Far-Eastern languages, as English and Korean⁵⁵.

Proverbs are used by speakers for a variety of purposes. Sometimes they are used as a way of saying something gently, in a veiled way. Other times, they are used to carry more weight in a discussion, a weak person is able to enlist the tradition of the ancestors to support his position, or even to argue a legal case. Proverbs can also be used to simply make conversation, discussion will be lively. In many parts of the world, the use of proverbs is a mark of being a good orator.

Paremiology is the collection and study of proverbs. Paremiography, on the other hand, is the collection of proverbs.

Through learning proverb we can give specific information about human`s language, the way of their life, their culture, their tradition and also their custom.

Proverbs are basic and specific sayings that are widely known and repeated that communicate a truth based on common sense or human experience. They are traditional sayings that provide advice or present a moral in a brief and succinct manner. Proverbs are frequently metaphorical. Maxims are proverbs that define a fundamental guideline of action. The study and collecting of proverbs is known as paremiology, and it dates back to Aristotle. A person who is interested in the study of proverbs is known as a paremiologist (a proverb scholar)⁵⁶.

proverb: a piece of common-sense wisdom expressed in practical, homely terms ("A stitch in time saves nine")

adage: is a time-honored and widely known saying ("Where there's smoke, there's fire")

⁵⁵ Arnold I.V. The English Word. – Moscow: Higher School Publishing House, 1973, p.33-37.

⁵⁶ Cruse D. A. Lexical Semantics, – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1986, p.187.

maxim: a general rule of behaviour drawn from practical experience ("Neither a borrower nor a lender be")

motto: a maxim adopted as a principal of conduct ("Honesty is the best policy")

epigram: is a brief, witty, or satirical statement that often gains effect through paradox ("The only way to get rid of temptation is to yield to it")

aphorism: similar to an epigram but more profound rather than witty ("He is a fool that cannot conceal his wisdom")⁵⁷

Proverbs are characterized by their features:

Every proverb appreciates any event both positively and negatively. Such kind of features serve to make the proverbs popular among people. Proverbs express wise and complete idea and sayings express the description of something but do not give complete meanings. They consist of one compositional element.

As for English language is characterized such genre of folklore as Proverbs. And in English proverbs are expressions of popular wisdom, historical memory, is a set of rules of life, practical philosophy, affecting virtually all spheres of life and situations.

In conclusion we can say that proverbs play a great role in a development of linguistics. The usage of paremies and other phraseological units can make our speech, lessons more persuasive and trustful. The significance of the proverb it is understanding its meaning. If their usage be in a right way, then the aim will be successful.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Arnold I.V. The English Word. – Moscow: Higher School Publishing House, 1973, p.33-37.
2. Cruse D. A. Lexical Semantics, – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1986, p.187.

⁵⁷ <https://student.zoomru.ru/ino/specific-features-of-proverbs-and/297157.3499990.s1.html>

3. International Encyclopedia of Unified Science. – Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press. 1955
4. <https://mylektsii.su/8-67153.html>
5. <https://student.zoomru.ru/ino/specific-features-of-proverbs-and/297157.3499990.s1.html>

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

Khodjaeva Muslimakhon Ravshanjon kizi

2nd year graduate student

Uzbekistan State World Languages University, Tashkent

Annotation. The article presents the concepts of language and culture as a means of communication and intercultural competence of an individual. Approaches to the study of the problem of continuous connection between language and culture are analysed by the author.

Keywords: culture, language, relationship between language and culture, communication

Human communication is one of the most significant topics on linguists', anthropologists', psychologists', and philosophers' thoughts today. Since it is the most important means of communication among human beings, the relation between language, culture, and their mutual interactions have high significance. The relevance of the problem "language and culture" was initially put forth by V. Humboldt, who claims that language expresses "the objective reality of the nation" and "cultural spirit" [1, 370-377]. He outlined the following basic concepts: 1) the material and spiritual cultures are embodied in language; 2) any culture has its national character presented in language; 3) language of one specific culture is an expression of "national spirit"; 4) the subject of "language and culture" is studied by an individual or community.